

THE ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MODERN MODELS OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *A large number of people who analyze the results of translation work are engaged in evaluating the quality of translation, identifying and classifying errors: editors, critics, customers, translation teachers, etc.*

Key words: *The situational-denotative model of translation, logical-syntactic connections, syntactic structure, specific languages.*

The translation model can be defined as a “conditional representation of the procedure for implementing the translation process”, a kind of hypothetical construction that displays the main stages of the translation process and the actions carried out by the translator at each stage. The problem of describing such actions is complicated by the fact that all of them are carried out in the mind of the translator, that is, they are not directly observable.

Currently, the following models are most widely used in translation theory: situational-denotative, transformational and semantic.

The situational-denotative model of translation proceeds from the fact that the content of all linguistic signs reflects some objects, phenomena, relations of reality. The objects of reality reflected in linguistic signs are called denotations. The situation in reality is a set of denotations and relations between them. Consequently, segments of speech contain information about some situation in reality. Transformational model of translation

The transformational model (theory) of translation is based on the provisions of the transformational (generating) grammar of N. Chomsky. Transformational grammar considers the rules for generating syntactic structures characterized by the commonality of lexemes and basic logical-syntactic connections. According to transformational grammar, the entire set of syntactic structures can be reduced to a limited number of elementary, core structures, in which the logical-syntactic relations are the most transparent. According to certain transformational rules, derivatives, surface structures are derived from nuclear structures.

The use of a transformational model to study translation activity seems to be very useful. V.N. Komissarov notes the following advantages of this model [3]:

- transformational theory assigns an important place to the comparative study of multilingual forms, between which relations of translation equivalence can be established, which creates a theoretical basis for describing the system of translation relations of two specific languages;

- the transformation model makes it possible to identify various types of translation transformations;

- an attempt to connect the process of translation with intralinguistic transformations is of undoubted value, since it makes it possible to explain the facts of the translation of structures of the foreign language that do not have correspondences in the translation language.

At the first stage of the translation process, this structure is transformed into a nuclear structure within the same language: “She writes letters poorly”. At the second stage, the nuclear structure of the foreign language is replaced by the nuclear structure of the translation language: “She writes letters badly”. And then the nuclear structure of the translation language unfolds into the surface structure of the native language: “She can’t write letters” [1].

At the same time, like every translation model, the transformational model is not without some drawbacks.

The semantic model of translation has significant explanatory power. It allows explaining many reasons for the semantic discrepancies between the two texts, points to a number of significant factors that determine the choice of translation option. However, it is not without a number of significant shortcomings.

According to V.N. Komissarov, it does not provide for such cases when different languages use different semantic categories to describe the same situation (instant coffee - instant coffee); it does not affect the problems of transferring figurative and other associations in translation, it passes by the multifaceted content of the text, the possibility of using units of the language in a figurative sense, relying on preliminary experience and the presence of associations that may turn out to be different and the recipients of the original and translation.

The main reproach expressed by V.N. Komissarov is that within the framework of the semantic model of translation there is no place for the category of the goal of communication, which plays a decisive role in the choice of means of translation [3].

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Komissarov V. N. Sovremennoe perevodovedenie [Modern Translation studies]. posobie. - M.: ETS, 2002.
2. G.T. Qodirova. Linguistic and communicative competence in learning language. International conference., 2016, p.441.
3. Usmonova Sh. Study of scientific technical transfusion in non-linguistic educational university. International journal. Moscow.2019.
4. Gak V.G., Lvin Yu.I. Practical translation course. - M., 1962.
5. N.A. Odilova., M.U. Irgashev. Information and communication technology in language learning. International conference., 2016, p.439.
6. Kazakova T.A. Practical foundations of translation. - SPb., 2000.
7. Retsker Ya.I. Translation Theory and Translation Practice - M.: International Relations, 1974.
8. Tyulenev S.V. Translation Theory - M.: GARDARIKI, 2004.
9. Egamberdiyeva D.U. Language learning with ICT: uses and issues. International conference., 2016, p.341.